

The Cairo International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD) and Other Landmarks in Demographic History

Alexander A. Tkachenko ¹

¹ *Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation, Moscow, 125167, Russia*

Received 31 May 2025 ♦ Accepted 14 August 2025 ♦ Published 25 November 2025

Citation: Tkachenko AA (2025) The Cairo International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD) and Other Landmarks in Demographic History. *Population and Economics* 9(4):128-142. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.9.e160794>

Abstract

This paper discusses anniversary events that we consider important in the field of demography in 2024–2025, including the birthdays of notable figures and significant conference dates, such as the International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD) held in Cairo, Egypt in 1994, as well as notable publications.

Keywords

international conferences on population, anniversaries of researchers, publications, demographic institutions

JEL codes: B10, B20, J10

Introduction

The year 2024 marks the 30th anniversary of the last international conference on population held in Cairo, Egypt in 1994, which undoubtedly went down in history. As noted in *Demographic Encyclopaedia* (Demograficheskaya ehnciklopediya 2013: 136), the expansion of the conference title compared to previous similar conferences represented two hypostases (ὑπό-στάσις) at once, although only one word was added, “development”. Firstly, this is a new emphasis by both the United Nations and the international community on the problems of social and economic development in the context of a growing world population on the one hand, and the demographic ageing of the population of the world’s leading economies, on the other. Secondly, it recognises the high dependence of development and economic growth in general on the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of population

growth. A significant part of the paper focuses on the Cairo Conference on Population and Development, and then we list some important events in the history of demography – anniversaries of scientists and memorable studies that have gone down in the history of demographic science.

Key points of the Cairo Conference

International conferences on population have been held for 70 years, which is almost equal to the world's population's average life expectancy at birth. As an important international institution for the exchange of views between experts and officials/governments from around the world, they are a valuable platform for discussion. The most recent conference, the International Conference on Population and Development, hereinafter referred to as ICPD, was held exactly 30 years ago in Cairo, Egypt. It had a profound impact on the social development of countries and regions, with far-reaching consequences in terms of both time and space. The ICPD added the term and concept of development to the title of the forum itself, becoming a conference on population and development, thus pointing to a paradigm for the future approach to population issues, which should be considered through the lenses of development of society, the economy, the environment, social institutions and government policy on population.

An ambitious theme was chosen for the conference: “Population, sustained economic growth and sustainable development.” Looking back over the last 30 years, we can see that the conference's guidelines have generally been implemented and the population development plans have been fulfilled. However, recent discussions within the UN system reveal that, even before the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, the principle of sustainable development had been violated, resulting in a departure from the previously achieved outcomes.¹

The ICPD can be viewed as a precursor to the UN Sustainable Development Agenda, adopted 20 years later, which sets out 17 goals, 169 targets and 232 unique indicators.²

The ICPD formulated a global strategy and action plan on population issues for the beginning of the 21st century. These issues encompass all spheres of human life, including family, household, and population of a territory or country. Therefore, setting targets and specific development goals on this scale will inevitably encroach on the development objectives of society and the country. This is independent of the nature of population reproduction and the ideological foundations of the national economic development/growth model.

It is noteworthy that the ICPD adopted the Programme of Action (United Nations 1995) designed for 20 years and approved by all the 179 participating countries, and 20 years later, in 2015, the UN adopted a new programme of action, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2018), encompassing the totality of human life: environment, economy, family well-being, social development and social inclusion. The seventeen UN Sustainable Development Goals for 2030 adopted as part of the Agenda replaced the UN Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). It is also worth noting

1 Shulla K (2021) The COVID-19 pandemic and the achievement of the SDGs. In: Virtual Inter-agency Expert Group Meeting on Implementation of the Third United Nations Decade for the Eradication of Poverty (2018–2027) “Accelerating Global Actions for a World without Poverty” 24–27 May 2021. URL: https://www.un.org/development/desa/dspd/wp-content/uploads/sites/22/2021/05/Shulla_paper1.pdf

2 UN SDGs, which have been cited in all papers on the Cairo Conference written after 2014.

that in honour of the ICPD's 20th anniversary, the Programme of Action was republished in 2004 with a new Introduction (United Nations 2014: 221-296).

The ICPD was recognised as a landmark that enabled countries to reach a universal consensus by placing human rights above all else. Following the ICPD, the goals set out in the Programme of Action, namely ensuring universal education and reduction of infant, child, and maternal mortality, were monitored by the UN agencies and summarised in reports submitted every five years.

The ICPD was the last one in a series of conferences held over seventy years.³ There were many reasons for this, including the titanic efforts required from not only the UN and its agencies, but also from host countries in preparing for and receiving so many government delegations, as well as new UN initiatives addressing population issues, and the emergence of new technologies of communication and organisation of summits.

Rather than a substitution for the ICPD, international conferences of parliamentarians began to be held to follow up on the implementation of the ICPD's Programme of Action. In 2002, the parliamentarians adopted the Ottawa Statement of Commitment, positioning themselves as representatives of public interests, legislators, and executive officers, whereby they committed to work towards the ICPD Programme on a systematic basis and actively monitor the progress in the population sector.

Since 2002, eight International Parliamentarians' Conferences on the Implementation of the ICPD Programme of Action have been held: Ottawa (2002), Strasbourg (2004), Bangkok (2006), Addis Ababa (2009), Istanbul (2012), Stockholm (2014), Ottawa (2018).⁴

In Bangkok, the parliamentarians reiterated that the international community had taken a concerted decision to allocate funds on an annual basis for the implementation of programmes in the population and reproductive health sector in developing countries. It should be remembered, however, that reproductive health issues concern the populations of all countries, including highly developed ones. We would also like to highlight two statements made in Bangkok: today, more than 350 million married couples do not have full access to family planning services, and population growth in developing countries continues to increase the burden on the environment.⁵ We deem these realities to be important for better understanding the positive shifts in the mindset of the global community and decision-makers that have taken place since the ICPD.

In 2024, a conference of parliamentarians from all regions of the world was held in Oslo, Norway, as highlighted in the Oslo Statement of Commitment, which took stock of the thirty years that passed since the ICPD. The meeting adopted the Oslo Statement of Commitment under the striking title "Life or Death is a Political Decision," which noted the progress made in adopting new legislations, policies, and programmes.

One can agree with the main message of the statement: "Our successes have placed individual dignity and human rights at the center of development"⁶ but at the same time, the indicators of above mentioned successes are noteworthy as they are – they include women's access to contraceptives, the number of girls having access to education, reduction in the

3 This is not counting the first World Population Conference held in Geneva in 1927. See: (Demograficheskaya ehnciklopediya 2013: 564-565).

4 Clearly, Ottawa's decision to hold the conferences once every two years has not been implemented as intended.

5 There are significant differences of opinion between developed and developing countries on issues of environmental balance (Tkachenko 2021: 24-27).

6 Oslo Statement of Commitment. The 8th International Parliamentarians' Conference on the Implementation of the ICPD Programme of Action (IPCI/ICPD) (2024) URL: <https://ipconference.org/>.

number of child marriages. These largely pertain not even to developing countries as such, but to the poorest among them. We believe that the UN (UNFPA) is primarily focused on the world's poorest and most vulnerable countries and territories, while the common problems of the global community are pushed into the background.

The Eighth Parliamentary Conference demonstrated the convergence of issues related to the implementation of the ICPD Programme of Action and the UN SDGs on the path towards 2030.⁷ However, the main objective is defined as mobilising resources and creating favourable conditions for sexual and reproductive health and rights. We believe that this rather narrows the main idea of the Cairo Summit on Development, although reproductive rights⁸ are one of the components of development in the population sector.

The ICPD is the subject matter of special reports by UNFPA published in 2004 (State of World Population 2004) and in 2011 (State of World Population 2011); besides, the UN monitors progress in achieving the ICPD goals on 11 indicators across all countries of the world, the findings of which are published regularly. UNFPA conferences have provided five-year implementation reviews of the Programme of Action, with inputs not only from national institutions but also from a diverse range of stakeholders who were involved in the discussions through UN-held events and dialogues.

Experts on the role and significance of the ICPD

John Wilmoth and Julia Bunting,⁹ leading UN experts on population, summarised the outcomes of the thirty years since the ICPD. They believe that new leaders need to reaffirm their commitment to the ICPD agenda. They noted that the following have become integral components of addressing population issues for all participating governments: sexual and reproductive health, reproductive rights, gender equality, environmental sustainability, and international cooperation, which were recognised as integral components of addressing population issues and achieving the development goals formulated by governments.¹⁰

Three decades later, the outcomes of the ICPD, primarily the Programme of Action, are considered to be an outstanding success based on the evolution of key indicators such as infant mortality, which has been halved; maternal mortality, which has fallen by 34% over the period; and the number of women using contraception, which has doubled.¹¹ The UN experts emphasise that population issues have been incorporated into national development strategies in countries around the world, and that governments' commitments to collecting demographic data have enabled policymakers to make informed decisions.

7 Oslo Statement of Commitment "Life or Death is a Political Decision". URL: https://www.epfweb.org/sites/default/files/2024-04/Oslo%20Statement%20of%20Commitment_12%20April%202024%2012_00%20pm%20-%20with%20logo%20%281%29.pdf

8 This may be one of the most pressing issues, particularly in the developing world, but it is not a key development issue for the global population as a whole.

9 John Wilmoth is Director, Population Division, United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UN DESA). Julia Bunting is Director, Programme Division, UNFPA.

10 Wilmoth J, Bunting J (2024) Thirty Years On, Leaders Need to Recommit to the International Conference on Population and Development Agenda. UN Chronicle. 26 April 2024. <https://www.un.org/en/un-chronicle/thirty-years-leaders-need-recommit-international-conference-population-and-development>.

11 United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2022). World Family Planning 2022: Meeting the changing needs for family planning: Contraceptive use by age and method. UN DESA/POP/2022/TR/NO. 4. P. i.

The role of the ICPD regarding reproductive health, the definition of which, as noted by V. Sakevich, was formulated and introduced into international practice precisely by the materials of this global forum, is of historical significance (Sakevich 2018). Family planning was at the centre of the most heated and often irreconcilable debates. Despite the subtle interpretation of this in many ways fundamental concept or even phenomenon by the UN Secretariat experts, opponents of family planning as such have argued that family planning aims to limit fertility in countries where it is high, and this point of view is still not infrequent¹². This incorrect assertion allows for family planning to be characterised as a state intervention, implemented through official policy, which infringes upon the reproductive rights of the family.

There is growing recognition among experts of the importance of local/municipal authorities in addressing the complex issues in the implementation of the ICPD Programme of Action. Effective local governance and equitable delivery of local public services are crucial for tailoring actions to the unique needs of communities, ensuring sustainable development and promoting inclusivity. We also believe that the uniqueness of local authorities/municipalities in addressing the problems of local population stems from the higher effectiveness of their actions resulting from their better knowledge of problems and needs of the local population.

In 2024, the UN experts wrote: “While our demographic trends diverge, our fates remain intertwined.”¹³ We believe that “intertwined fates” and “supporting those hardest to reach” do not suggest an ever-increasing reliance on support from the most developed countries to the least developed, nor an escalating demand for such support. Rather, they should refer to the most socially vulnerable members of society. For example, in order to fulfil the UN SDG on environmental sustainability, the Fund for Responding to Loss and Damage was established at COP28¹⁴ (2023) to help vulnerable populations in the least developed countries. The Fund is expected to allocate approximately K100 billion annually to those countries to help them cope with the effects of climate change. The Fund’s total commitments exceed K660 million, which is considered insufficient to address the inevitable and irreversible consequences of the climate emergency. Some estimates of the required financial coverage are significantly higher, reaching up to K400 billion per year (Vaidyanathan 2024).

A brief history of demographic institutions and societies

It is the **95th anniversary** of the Population Association of America (PAA), a non-profit research professional association that studies issues associated with population and demography. The PAA was founded by H.P. Fairchild,¹⁵ a researcher on race relations, abortion, contraception, immigration, one of the founders of Planned Parenthood, president of the American Eugenics Society (1929–1931), and F.H. Osborn, a well-known eugenics researcher in the post-WWII period. The Milbank Memorial Fund, a charitable fund fo-

12 For example, the Institute for Family Studies has levelled such attacks at the United Nations Fund for Population Activities report (State of World Population 2023).

13 Wilmoth J, Bunting J (2024) Thirty Years On, Leaders Need to Recommit to the International Conference on Population and Development Agenda. UN Chronicle. 26 April 2024. <https://www.un.org/en/un-chronicle/thirty-years-leaders-need-recommit-international-conference-population-and-development>.

14 Annual United Nations Climate Change Conference, or Conference of the Parties - COP.

15 In 2025, we commemorate the 145th anniversary of his birth.

cusing on public health policy, provided the funding. During its early years, the PAA was a coalition of population scientists, advocates of active birth control measures, supporters of immigration restrictions, and eugenicists. It holds annual conferences, the first of which was held in New York in April 1932. The PAA has sponsored such notable conferences as the Conference on Population Estimates held in New York City in 1935, which was attended by Eleanor Roosevelt, and the conference “Integrating Genetics and the Social Sciences” held at the Institute of Behavioral Science on the University of Colorado Boulder campus in 2013. The PAA publishes *Demography*, a premier journal established in 1964, issued six times annually by Duke University Press, and recognised globally for its authoritative research on population dynamics and demographic trends.

L’Institut national d’études démographiques (INED, The French Institute for Demographic Studies), which was established by a decree of the French government under De Gaulle in 1945, is celebrating its **80th** anniversary.¹⁶ The Institute is world-renowned as one of the main centres of demographic research and has collaborated with Russian researchers and demographic institutions. Monographs by INED staff members have been published in Russia, among others, on demographic processes in Russia. The INED’s contribution to research into Russian demographic history and identification of many gaps there is particularly noteworthy. The French government’s interest in an institution like the INED, as evidenced by government decrees of 1945 and 1986¹⁷, may serve as a role model for other countries.

The European Doctoral School of Demography celebrates its **20th anniversary**. Each year, students with diverse academic backgrounds ranging from mathematics and statistics to biology and history enrol in the School’s 11-month programme to acquire high-quality knowledge in demography as they get prepared for their doctoral studies. The training takes place at two leading European demography research institutions: the basic preparatory courses take place at the Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research while the core courses, at the French Institute for Demographic Studies. Apart from training per se, the School considers it important that the students enjoy excellent networking opportunities in the community of recognised demographers across Europe. The School operates under the auspices of the European Association for Population Studies. The training programme is also supported by 17 leading European organisations in the field of demography, including universities and research centres, who provide teachers, administrative staff, consulting mentors, scholarships, and coverage of related expenses. Each year, 15–20 doctoral students graduate from the School with an expertise in mathematical demography, theory, and policy. The anniversary will be celebrated at the European Population Conference 2026, to be held in Bologna, Italy, on 3–6 June 2026.

Milestones in Research: Celebrating Historic Publication Anniversaries

It is **130 years** of the study by **Ernst Engel** (Engel, Christian Lorenz Ernst) “Die Lebenskosten belgischer Arbeiter-Familien früher und jetzt”. In 1895, this famous German statistician¹⁸ who taught statistics at the University of Berlin alongside his main work, published

16 Ordonnance n°45-2499 du 24 octobre 1945 creation de l’Institut qui se substitue a la “fondation française pour l’étude des problèmes humains”.

17 Décret n°86-382 du 12 mars 1986 portant organisation et fonctionnement de l’Institut national d’études démographiques.

18 For more details see: (Tkachenko 2017).

a seminal paper on the cost of living for Belgian working-class families. The author, based on an analysis of family budgets of Belgian workers using data provided by E.A. von Duetiaux, identified patterns that became known in research and practice as Engel's law (Engel 1895). It was first formulated in 1857 and still plays an important role in the study of income differentiation among families and households. Engel's research aimed to find conditions for the balanced development of production and consumption that would correspond to population growth, i.e. the so-called law of population. To this end, Engel studied Malthusian population theory and the sectoral distribution of labour. Regrettably, the authors of numerous definitions of the "socialist law of population" did not seem to have been familiar with E. Engel's works. Contemporary demographers, sociologists, and economists should be grateful to Engel, who was the first to formulate in the above paper the "adult consumption equivalent" (Grings 2007) by weighing the consumption of individual household members according to age and gender. This study is still relevant today for estimating the household income elasticity for food (Benda-Prokeinová et al. 2017).

170 years ago, a book by the French statistician and demographer **Achille Guillard** was published in Paris, where he used the word "demography" for the first time. The very title of the book, *Éléments de statistique humaine ou démographie comparée où sont exposés les principes de la science nouvelle, et confrontés, d'après les documents les plus authentiques, l'état, les mouvements généraux et les progrès de la population dans les pays civilisés* (Guillard 1855), states that it sets forth the principles of the new field of science, comparative demography. Two years before the book was published, Guillard spoke at the first session of the International Statistical Congress in Brussels, Belgium, outlining the principles of organisation of population statistics. The book has been republished in the *Forgotten Books* series; the latest edition was out in 2019. The book has not been translated into Russian¹⁹.

It is 80 years since the publication of the book *Ocherki po istorii statistiki 17-18 vekov* (Essays on the History of Statistics in the 17th and 18th Centuries) by **Mikhail Vasilyevich Ptukha** (Ptukha 1945), corresponding member of the USSR Academy of Sciences (1943), founder and director of the Institute of Demography of the Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (1919-1934). The book specifically focuses on demographic development in France from the mid-18th to the early 19th century (Section VII), population statistics of Sweden (Section VI) and the works by political arithmeticians²⁰.

55 years ago, **Boris Urlanis** wrote his famous paper *Beregite muzhchin!* (Take Care of Men!)²¹ introducing the concept of male supermortality into the Russian demography. In 1968, the year of its publication, the gap in life expectancy between men and women in the USSR was eight years. By the year this prominent Russian demographer died, the gap had grown to 10.2 years, and the maximum gap of 13.6 years occurred in 2005. The gap was nearly the same at 13.5 years in 1995 and 2004, which was the clear sign of the demographic crisis. The problem raised in the above paper and the challenge formulated by B. Urlanis regarding male supermortality remain acute and highly relevant more than half a century later.

19 A copy of the original (422 pages) is available at: <https://dn790002.ca.archive.org/0/items/lmentsdestatist01guilgoog/lmentsdestatist01guilgoog.pdf>.

20 The book is available at: <https://www.booksite.ru/fulltext/184377/index.html>.

21 Urlanis B (1968) *Beregite muzhchin* [Take Care of Men]. *Literaturnaya gazeta* N 30. 24 July 1968.

Honouring Milestones: Anniversaries of Researchers Who Shaped Demography

It is **405** years since the birth of John Graunt (1620-1674), the founder of demographic research, an English statistician who was a successful haberdasher before Great Fire of London in 1666 (Demograficheskaya ehnciklopediya 2013: 198-199). Graunt's book *Natural and Political Observations Made upon the Bills of Mortality* (Graunt 1662), which analysed statistics on the natural movement of London's population, is considered to have had a significant influence on the pioneering demographic work of William Petty and, even more importantly, as Britannica points out,²² that of Edmond Halley. Analysing mortality records in London parishes based on data since 1532, he discovered a regularity in certain phenomena in mortality statistics, which inspired his famous work. The book went through four editions during the author's lifetime, the third of which was published in 1665 by the Royal Society, of which Graunt was a founding member. The fifth edition, published after the author's death in 1676, contained a note added to the title: [Sometimes attributed to Sir W. Petty]. Graunt classified mortality rates according to causes of death and showed that mortality rates in cities exceed those in rural areas, and that the higher rate of men's births is offset by men's higher mortality. The mortality table is considered to be his most important innovation: by using only two survival indicators, up to 6 and up to 76 years, he projected the percentages of people who lived to reach each subsequent age and their life expectancy.

It is **270** years since the birth of **Ivan Filippovich Herman** (born Benedikt Franz Johann von Hermann), a foreign (Austrian) honorary member of the Russian Imperial Academy of Sciences (1786), who was also a member of seven other foreign academies and societies. A scientist and engineer possessing versatile and profound knowledge, he was in Russian service since 1782. He is the author of the work Hermann Benedikt Franz Johann (1790) *Statistische Schilderung von Russland, in Rücksicht auf Bevölkerung, Landesbeschaffenheit, Naturprodukte, Landwirtschaft, Bergbau, Manufakturen und Handel*. St. Petersburg; Leipzig, 488 s.) ("Statistical Description of Russia in Terms of Population, Land Characteristics, Natural Products, Agriculture, Mining, Manufacturing and Trade")²³. He also put forward the idea of "single-day population registration," which was implemented during the First General Census of the Russian Empire in 1897. In 1806, the Academy of Sciences' Statistical Journal published his work *O narodonaselenii. O sostavlenii i upotreblenii narodnykh tablits* ("On Population. On the Compilation and Use of Population Tables"). He wrote the history of statistics on natural population movement, starting with the time of Peter I, in his work "Memoir on Births, Marriages and Deaths in Some Provinces and Cities of Russia" (in French), pointing out the importance of the unity of these statistics with other branches of statistics for maximum benefit.²⁴

It is **190** years since the birth of **Yuliy Eduardovich Yanson**, researcher, educator, statistician, political economist and demographer (population statistics), Doctor of Political Econ-

22 John Graunt. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/John-Graunt>

23 Available from the Electronic Library of the State Public Historical Library of Russia at: <http://elib.shpl.ru/nodes/26397-hermann-v-f-j-statistische-schilderung-von-russland-in-rucksicht-auf-bevolkerung-landesbeschaffenheit-naturprodukte-landwirtschaft-bergbau-manufakturen-und-handel-st-petersburg-leipzig-1790>.

24 250 let so dnya rozhdeniya Ivana Filippovicha Germana (1755 - 1815) [250th anniversary of the birth of Ivan Filippovich German]. Demoscope Weekly. N 205-206, 2005. URL: <https://www.demoscope.ru/weekly/2005/0205/nauka01.php>.

omy and Statistics (1871), professor (1873), corresponding member of the Russian Imperial Academy of Sciences (1892), member of the International Statistical Institute. During his nearly 30 years of teaching in St. Petersburg, he was dean of the Faculty of Law and served as rector of the Imperial St. Petersburg University. In 1872, at the Eighth International Statistical Congress (St. Petersburg), he presented a report entitled “On the Registration and Publication of Facts of Natural Population Movement.”²⁵ In 1873, he published four works on demography in the journal *Znanie* (Knowledge): on birth rates, on mortality (two), and on marriages. In 1878, the first volume of Yanson’s *Comparative Statistics*, focusing on population statistics, was published. The *Theory of Statistics* (1891, third edition) was awarded the full prize of the Imperial Academy of Sciences and Count D.A. Tolstoy Gold Medal (1892). He established sanitary statistics at the St. Petersburg City Duma (Council) and initiated a campaign for the organisation of public relief for the poor. Having organised and headed the St. Petersburg Statistical Bureau, he introduced a card-based system for collecting economic and demographic data on population broken down by social strata. He organised the 1881 and 1890 population censuses in St. Petersburg, which were successful in a remarkable way, “unlike other cities in Russia or indeed many cities in Western Europe” (Georgievsky 1893). The methodology used in these censuses served as a basis for the papers he wrote for the magazine *Severny Vestnik*, entitled “*Ob ustroystve perepisey v gorodakh*” (On the organisation of censuses in cities) and “*O tekhnike perepisey naseleniya v primeneni k russkim gorodam*” (On the population census technique as applied to Russian cities) (1891).

It is **130** years since the birth of **Grigory Abramovich Batkis**, corresponding member of the USSR Academy of Medical Sciences (1945), healthcare official in the 1930s–1950s, specialist in social hygiene and sanitary statistics. In the 1920s, he laid the foundation for a course on Soviet social hygiene in university education (Moscow State University). He published a summary of his methodological work during his creative life in “*Anamnesticheskiy metod v demograficheskoy statistike*” (The Anamnestic Method in Demographic Statistics) (Batkis 1959).

It is **120** years since the birth of **Mikhail Veniaminovich Kurman**. He started his career in statistics under the guidance of S.A. Novoselsky and V.V. Paevsky. Development of tables representing the demographic catastrophe in the USSR in the 1930s was his historical achievement. By combining economic and sociological approaches to the study of staff turnover in enterprises, he coined the term social migration. He was a unique personality – after he was repressed for his extraordinarily bold behaviour and removed from society for 18.5 years, he was morally and physically strong enough to resume creative work in research, teaching, and service in statistical agencies. His repression was triggered by his memo defending the findings of the 1937 census. His last monograph was published in 1976 dealing with topical issues in demography. During his last years, he participated in discussions on methodological approaches to the publication of the world’s first demographic encyclopaedic dictionary.

It is **120th** anniversary of the birth and **50th** anniversary of the death of **Vladimir Nikonovich Starovsky**, corresponding member of the USSR Academy of Sciences (1958), long-serving head of the USSR statistical service (1940–1975), who made a significant contribution to the preparation and conduct of population censuses, starting with the 1939 cen-

25 The original title “*Enregistrement et publication des faits relatifs au mouvement de la population*” was published in the Congress Report.

sus. Under his leadership, the Scientific and Methodological Council of the Central Statistical Administration of the USSR was created (1948); the journal *Vestnik Statistiki* (Statistics Bulletin) was resumed (1949), which published statistical data not included in official compilations; a publishing house for statistical literature was established; publication began of the statistical yearbooks *Narodnoye Khozyaystvo SSSR* (The National Economy of the USSR) (1957); and finally, the Scientific Research Institute of Statistics was established (1963), including a demography department. (Bobrakov 2022) contains his most complete biography.

It is **110 years** since the birth of **Timon Vasilyevich Ryabushkin**, corresponding member of the USSR Academy of Sciences, USSR representative on the international arena in bodies such as the United Nations Population Commission, the United Nations Statistical Commission, and the International Statistical Institute. Ryabushkin was the organiser and chairman of the Scientific Council of the USSR Academy of Sciences on Socio-economic Problems of Population, in which members of the Population Centre of the Moscow State University including D.I. Valentey took an active part. Among the many milestones in the research by Ryabushkin, an expert with profound knowledge, we can highlight his work as head of the Department of Statistical Methodology of the USSR Central Statistical Administration, editor-in-chief of the State Publishing House of Statistical Literature, director of the Institute of Sociological Research of the USSR Academy of Sciences, and head of the Department of Demography and Statistics of the Central Economic and Mathematical Institute of the USSR Academy of Sciences.

It is **100 years** since the birth of **Edvard Arturovich Arab-Ogly**, author of two papers in the first demographic encyclopaedic edition, one on Geopolitics and another on Global Population Issues, where he highlighted the difference of approach to the study of these problems between bourgeois and Marxist scientists.²⁶ To his credit as a scientist, this approach was not to be found in the next edition of *Narodonaseleniye. Entsiklopedicheskiy slovar'* (Population. Encyclopaedic Dictionary),²⁷ although he criticised the concept of zero population growth. His work on Some Problems of Population was published in the journal *Voprosy filosofii* (Problems of Philosophy) as early as 1957 (Arab-Ogly 1957). He participated in monographic publications of the Population Centre edited by D.I. Valentey. He made a significant contribution to domestic research on population and demography in relation to social forecasting and globalism.

It is the **80th** anniversary of the birth of **James W. Vaupel**, an American demographer who specialised in population ageing research and biodemography and played a key role in developing the idea of plasticity of longevity (for more details, see (Loewenberg 2009; Schwentker 2010)).

He was the Founding Director of the Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research in Rostock, Germany (1996–2018); Director of the Duke Aging Center, and Research Professor at Duke University, North Carolina, USA. He pioneered research on the heterogeneity of mortality risks and on the deceleration of death rates at the highest ages. One of his most cited papers, (Vaupel 2010), was published in 2010²⁸.

26 Demograficheskij ehnciklopedicheskij slovar' [Demographic Encyclopedic Dictionary] (1985) The Great Soviet Encyclopedia, Moscow, 92 pp.

27 Narodonaselenie. Ehnciklopedicheskij slovar' [Population. Encyclopedic Dictionary] (1994) Melikyan GG (Ed.). The Great Russian Encyclopedia, Moscow, pp. 83–85. (In Russ.)

28 Detailed information about the honouree's main achievements can be found in: Professor James W. Vaupel. "Demography". Presented on the occasion of the Annual Assembly of the European Science Foundation, 23 November 2011. https://user.demogr.mpg.de/jwv/pdf/111123_vaupel_latsis_2011.pdf.

He was the Member of the German National Academy of Sciences Leopoldina, the National Academy of Sciences of the United States, the American Academy of Arts and Sciences, and scientific member of the Max Planck Society. He was the recipient of prestigious awards, including the Irene B. Taeuber Award for research achievements of the Population Association of America (2001), the European Latsis Prize (2011), and the Mindel C. Sheps Award in Mathematical Demography (2008).

It is 80 years since the birth of **Viktor Mikhailovich Medkov**, a graduate of the Department of Population Studies at the Faculty of Economics of Moscow State University, who worked for 20 years at the Centre for the Study of Population Problems and then at the Department of Family Sociology and Demography at the Faculty of Sociology of Moscow State University. Having defended his thesis in sociology, Mr Medkov fruitfully combined demography, sociology, and economics in his research, which gave his work special value. He authored a seminal textbook on demography that has been reprinted many times. By continuing the tradition established by D.I. Valentey of cooperation with demographic centres of the USSR constituent republics, Mr Medkov provided significant scientific and publication support to demographers in Central Asian countries. His awards include the Pitirim Sorokin Prize and the commemorative medal for the 250th anniversary of Moscow State University, but these fail to give him the full credit he deserves for his achievements. He is the author of papers in the Demographic encyclopaedic dictionary and in *Narodonaseleniye. Entsiklopedicheskiy slovar'* (Narodonaseleniye. Ehnciklopedicheskij slovar' 1994).

In 2025, we celebrate the 75th birthday of **Tatyana Leonidovna Kharkova**, a renowned demographer whose works on health, fertility and mortality are widely cited. Ms. Kharkova combines her research activities with teaching at the Department of Demography at the National Research University Higher School of Economics. (Tkachenko 2023) mentions the publication by T.L. Kharkova et al., *Naseleniye Sovetskogo Soyuzo 20 let nazad* (Population of the Soviet Union 20 years ago), as a major achievement in the Russian demographic science, and the author has many such achievements to her credit. Her colleagues are undoubtedly right in testifying to that she has devoted her entire life to the study of demographic processes.

This year marks the 70th birthday of **Alexander Alexandrovich Avdeev**, graduate of the Department of Population Studies at the Faculty of Economics of Moscow State University, head of the Information, Bibliographic and Historical Research Sector at the Centre for Population Studies, who combines this work with teaching and research at the Institut de démographie de l'Université de Paris (Institute of Demography at the University of Paris) and at the Centre de recherches de Institut de démographie de l'Université de Paris (Research Centre of the Institute of Demography). His colleagues note his meticulous attitude to sources and references – indeed, an important trait for any researcher and especially an expert in historical demography. That is not something that can be said about everyone. Then again, not everyone works at a world-renowned university. We hope that under such a leader, bibliographic work at the Faculty of Economics of Moscow State University will continue to develop successfully.

In 2025, we celebrate the 70th birthday of **Ekaterina Mikhailovna Shcherbakova**, a graduate of the Faculty of Economics at Moscow State University and, according to her colleagues, a longtime, regular, and invaluable contributor to *Demoscope Weekly* (Demographic Barometer section) and an impeccable professional. Ms. Shcherbakova is a permanent member of the team of authors of *Naseleniye Rossii* (Russia's Population), an annual analytical review that has been published regularly for over 30 years. A profound analyst,

she conducts research at the Institute of Economic Forecasting of the Russian Academy of Sciences and at the Vishnevsky Institute of Demography, thus contributing to their successful research on the population of Russia and the world.

In Memoriam: Honouring Late Demographers

This year marks the **60th** anniversary of the passing of Corrado Gini (1884-1965), one of the greatest European statisticians of the 20th century, the founder of the Italian school of statistics, who is also known as a demographer, sociologist, and eugenicist. Mr Gini received a broad education in subjects including law, mathematics, economics, and biology at the Faculty of Law of the University of Bologna (graduating as Doctor of Jurisprudence with Honours in 1905). He served as professor at the University of Cagliari (1909), University of Padua (1913), and the Sapienza University of Rome (1925). At the latter university, he pioneered the teaching of sociology, considering its subject to be the study of population and its measurable characteristics. At the Sapienza University of Rome, he founded the School of Statistics (1928) and the Faculty of Statistical, Demographic and Actuarial Sciences (1936; he also served as the dean from 1936 to 1954). He was the president and founder of the Central Institute of Statistics (later L'Istituto nazionale di statistica, the National Institute of Statistics) in Rome (1926-1932), which he established as the single Italian statistical service.

Demography and the study of population remained one of Mr Gini's main interests throughout his life. His first published work provides a detailed analysis of the sex ratio at birth and of earlier theories on this phenomenon, offering evidence of a certain degree of inheritance of the tendency to produce offspring of one sex or the other (Gini 1908). In studying population and its measurable characteristics, Mr Gini relied on biological concepts for a better understanding of social development. Later on, he put forward a cyclical theory of populations. His most famous contribution to science is the development of the Gini coefficient, which is used to measure the dispersion of concentration; its widespread application that only increased with time concerns the matters of income distribution and social inequality. Most countries and international organisations calculate the Gini coefficient, allowing to trace the evolution of modern standards of well-being in countries and societies. Its popularity is also explained by the clarity of its graphical representation using the Lorenz curve. Mr Gini made a significant contribution to demographic statistics by his studies of differential fertility, migration, and population evolution. In 1929, he founded the Italian Committee for the Study of Population Problems (Comitato italiano per lo studio dei problemi della popolazione), which conducted the first International Congress for Studies on Population in Rome in 1931. The activities of the Committee in the study of population problems and international dissemination of eugenics knowledge in the 1920s-1940s are discussed in detail in (Berlivet 2016).

Mr Gini founded the journals *Metron* (1920); *La vita economica italiana* (Italian Economic Life), published from 1926 to 1943; *Indici del movimento economico italiano* (Indices of the Italian economic movement (1926); and *GENUS* (1934), published under the auspices of the Italian Association for Demographic Research. He held honorary degrees from universities in Argentina, Italy, the USA, and Switzerland, and was president of a number of international societies and institutions. Some of Mr Gini's works on statistics have been translated into Russian.

The year of **2025** marks the passing of several well-known demographic researchers.

William Ward Kingkade (1954-2025), demographer and statistician, renowned analyst and forecaster of socio-demographic processes in the USA and in the USSR, and then, after 1989, in the countries of the former USSR; member of the United States Census Bureau.

Antonio Golini (1937-2025), Italian demographer and statistician, professor of demography at the Sapienza University of Rome (Sapienza Università di Roma) and at the LUISS University (Luiss-Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali). Founder and director of the Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies of the National Research Council (CNR) (1980-1997), director of the journal *Genus* (1993-2008) founded by Corrado Gini in 1934.

Jorge Martínez Pizarro (1959-2025), Chilean expert on international migration in Latin America, who devoted his professional career to the Latin American and Caribbean Demographic Centre (Centro Latinoamericano y Caribeño de Demografía, CELADE). Until his retirement in 2024, he was also editor of *Notas de Población*, CELADE's research journal.

References

- Arab-Ogly EA (1957) Nekotorye problemy narodonaseleniya [Some Problems of Population]. *Voprosy Filosofii* 6: 102-8. (In Russ.)
- Batkis GA (1959) Anamnesticheskiy metod v demograficheskoy statistike [The Anamnestic Method in Demography] In: Nemchinov IS (Ed.) *Problems of Demographic Statistics. Scientific Notes on Statistics of the USSR Academy of Sciences*. Gosstatizdat, Moscow, 188-210. (In Russ.)
- Benda-Prokeinová R, Dobeš K, Mura L, Buleca J (2017) Engel's approach as a tool for estimating consumer behaviour. *E&M Economics and Management* 20(2): 15–29. <https://doi.org/10.15240/tul/001/2017-2-002>.
- Berlivet LA (2016) A laboratory for Latin eugenics: the Italian Committee for the Study of Population Problems and the international circulation of eugenic knowledge, 1920s-1940s. *História, Ciências, Saúde – Manguinhos*: 23(Suppl 1): 51–72. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0104-59702016000500004>
- Bobrakov I (2022) Vladimir Nikonovich Starovskij (Seriya «Respublika Komi: lyudi i vremYA») [Vladimir Nikonovich Starovsky (Series “Komi Republic: People and Time”)]. Eskom Publishing House, Syktyvkar, 238 pp. (In Russ.)
- Demograficheskaya ehnciklopediya [Demographic Encyclopedia] (2013) “Encyclopedia” Publishing House, Moscow, 944 pp. (In Russ.)
- Demograficheskij ehnciklopedicheskij slovar' [Demographic Encyclopedic Dictionary] (1985) *The Great Soviet Encyclopedia*, Moscow, 92 pp. (In Russ.)
- Engel E (1895) *Die Lebenskosten belgischer Arbeiterfamilien früher und jetzt. Ermittelt aus Familien Haushaltrechnungen und vergleichend zusammengestellt*. Dresden: C. Heinrich.
- Georgievsky PI (1893) Professor Yulij Ehdvardovich Yanson, kak uchenyj i kak obshchestvennyj deyatel' [Professor Julius Eduardovich Yanson as a Scientist and as a Public Figure]. *Type. Homes for the Care of the Poor*, St. Petersburg, 8 pp. (In Russ.)
- Gini C (1908) *Il Sesso Dal Punto Di Vista Statistico: Le Leggi Della Produzione Dei Sessi*. Kessinger Publishing, 558 pp. Reprints, 2010.
- Graunt J (1662) Natural and political observations mentioned in a following index, and made upon the bills of mortality by John Graunt...; with reference to the government, religion, trade, growth,

- ayre, diseases, and the several changes of the said city. London: Printed by Tho. Roycroft for John Martin, James Allestry, and Tho. Dicas...
- Grings M (2007) Ernst Engels Entdeckung vor 150 Jahren. *Agrarwirtschaft: Zeitschrift für Betriebswirtschaft, Marktforschung und Agrarpolitik* 56 (7): 293-296. <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/304718>
- Guillard A (1855) *Éléments de statistique humaine ou démographie comparée*. Ined Éditions, Paris, 393 pp.
- Hermann BFJ (1790) *Statistische Schilderung von Russland, in Rücksicht auf Bevölkerung, Landesbeschaffenheit, Naturprodukte, Landwirtschaft, Bergbau, Manufakturen und Handel*. St. Petersburg; Leipzig. 488 s.
- Loewenberg S (2009) James Vaupel: an innovator in the demography of ageing. *The Lancet* 374(9696): 1139. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(09\)61729-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(09)61729-3)
- Narodonaselenie. Ehnciklopedicheskij slovar' [Population. Encyclopedic Dictionary] (1994) Melikyan GG (Ed.). *The Great Russian Encyclopedia*, Moscow, 608 pp. (In Russ.)
- Ptukha MV (1945) Ocherki po istorii statistiki XVII–XVIII vekov [Essays on the History of Statistics of the 17th-18th Centuries]. Nemchinov VS (Ed.). *Gospolitzdat*, Moscow, 352 pp. (In Russ.)
- Sakevich VI (2018) Politika v oblasti reproduktivnogo zdorov'ya v regionakh i stranakh mira [Reproductive Health Policy in Regions and Countries of the World]. *Demoscope Weekly N 777-778*. (In Russ.). <http://demoscope.ru/weekly/2018/0777/barom01.php>.
- Schwentker B (2010) So viel Leben. *Wissenschaftsmagazin – MaxPlanckForschung*: 1: 84-90.
- State of World Population 2004. The Cairo Consensus at Ten: Population, Reproductive Health and the Global Effort to End Poverty (2004) UNFPA, 2004. URL: https://www.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/swp04_eng.pdf
- State of World Population 2011. People and Possibilities in a World of 7 Billion (2011) UNFPA, 2011. URL: <https://www.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/EN-SWOP2011-FINAL.pdf>
- State of World Population 2023. 8 Billion Lives, Infinite Possibilities: The Case for Rights and Choices (2023) United Nations Population Fund, 2023, 192 pp. <https://doi.org/10.18356/9789210027137>
- The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2018 (2018). New York: United Nations, 2018.
- Tkachenko AA (2017) Reform Era in German statistics and E. Engel. *Voprosy statistiki* (5): 75-84. (In Russ.)
- Tkachenko AA (2021) Is the transition to a new climate economy possible? *Economics, taxes & law* 14(4): 15-29. (In Russ.). [10.26794/1999-849X-2021-14-4-15-29](https://doi.org/10.26794/1999-849X-2021-14-4-15-29)
- Tkachenko AA (2023) The centennial anniversary of the first census of urban population in the USSR and other achievements of researchers in the present and past in the field of population studies. *Population and Economics* 7 (4): 124-149. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.7.e118478>
- United Nations (1995) *Population and Development. Programme of Action adopted at the International Conference on Population and Development, Cairo, 5–13 September 1994*.
- United Nations (2014) *International Conference on Population and Development. Programme of Action. Twentieth Anniversary Edition*. UNFPA, 296 pp.
- Vaidyanathan G (2024) A giant fund for climate disasters will soon open. Who should be paid first? *Nature*, 29.01.2024. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-00149-x>
- Vaupel JW (2010) Biodemography of human ageing. *Nature* 464 : 536–542. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08984>

Other sources of information

250 let so dnya rozhdeniya Ivana Filippovicha Germana (1755 - 1815) [250th anniversary of the birth of Ivan Filippovich German]. Demoscope Weekly. N 205-206, 2005. URL: <https://www.demoscope.ru/weekly/2005/0205/nauka01.php>

John Graunt. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/John-Graunt>.

Oslo Statement of Commitment “Life or Death is a Political Decision”. URL: https://www.epfweb.org/sites/default/files/2024-04/Oslo%20Statement%20of%20Commitment_12%20April%202024%2012_00%20pm%20-%20with%20logo%20%281%29.pdf

Shulla K (2021) The COVID-19 pandemic and the achievement of the SDGs. In: Virtual Inter-agency Expert Group Meeting on Implementation of the Third United Nations Decade for the Eradication of Poverty (2018-2027) “Accelerating Global Actions for a World without Poverty” 24-27 May 2021. URL: https://www.un.org/development/desa/dspd/wp-content/uploads/sites/22/2021/05/Shulla_paper1.pdf

The 8th International Parliamentarians’ Conference on the Implementation of the ICPD Programme of Action (IPCI/ICPD) (2024) URL: <https://ipciconference.org/>

United Nations. Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2022) World Family Planning 2022: Meeting the changing needs for family planning: Contraceptive use by age and method. UN DESA/POP/2022/TR/NO. 4.

Urlanis B (1968) Beregite muzhchin [Take Care of Men]. Literaturnaya gazeta N 30. 24 July.

Wilmoth J, Bunting J (2024) Thirty Years On, Leaders Need to Recommit to the International Conference on Population and Development Agenda. UN Chronicle. 26 April 2024. URL: <https://www.un.org/en/un-chronicle/thirty-years-leaders-need-recommit-international-conference-population-and-development>

Information about the author

- Tkachenko Alexander Alexandrovich – Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Prof., Chief Researcher at the Institute of International Economic Relations Research, Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation. Moscow, 125167, Russia. E-mail: alaltkachenko@gmail.com